

The initial sheath blight severity on the source plants was determined 12 d after source establishment as the percent leaf and stem areas covered by lesions on a sample of five tillers. Leaf wetness assessments at the upper, middle, and lower layer of the crop canopy were made using a four-point assessment scale where 0 = dry, 1 = few, scattered, big droplets, 2 = thin film of small droplets, and 3 = dense film of small droplets. All assessments were made at 0600 h and data were taken on 10 dates after inoculation on a sample of 10 hills in each N treatment.

Contact frequency between plants was assessed during stem elongation, booting, and ripening stages from counts of leaf-to-leaf and leaf-to-sheath contacts of a reference hill with its neighbors.

Hills were sampled during the same growth stages to determine the percent N content using the Kjeldahl method.

The mean rate of focus expansion (R) was computed as:

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (a_{i+1} - a_i) / (t_{i+1} - t_i)}{n-1}$$

where n = the number of observations (six for each experiment), a_i = the focus areas in cm^2 at sample time i , and t_i = the number of days after inoculation at sample time i .

The data from the WS and DS experiments were combined and averaged across replicates. Path analysis was performed with the log-transformed mean rate of focus expansion (F) values as the response variable and the variables listed in the table as regressors.

The path diagram (see figure) suggests a marginal direct effect of N content on the rate of focus expansion, and strong indirect effects via canopy wetness and contact frequency. The analysis suggests that the latter two variables might be major driving factors in disease spread. The direct effect of initial severity on the upper leaf layer of the source plant on focal expansion is stronger than that of initial severity on the lower layer.

Path analysis can be used to describe complex data sets by means of direct and indirect effects on a response variable despite the confounding effects caused by multicollinearity of the explanatory variables. This study further demonstrates

that path analysis can be a useful tool in understanding the rice-sheath blight pathosystem by showing which variables exert influences on the spread of the disease and by uncovering the influences of these variables on each other. ■

Selection of protein content of upland rice grain using chlorophyll content

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Breeding for protein content is important to improve the nutritive value and taste of rice. However, the complicated analysis of protein content is inadequate as a breeding technique. We tried to establish a method for selecting protein content of brown rice by measuring chlorophyll content before harvest.

Fourteen varieties of both Japanese upland and lowland rices were cultivated under the usual conditions. The chlorophyll content of the top unfolded leaves of five plants of each variety was measured about every 2 wk with a chlorophyll-measuring instrument (SPAD-502, Minolta). After harvest, protein content

of brown rice was measured by Kjeldahl method.

Chlorophyll content and protein content of both upland and lowland rice were not correlated until 15 d before heading (DBH). However, chlorophyll content of upland rice from 15 DBH correlated significantly with protein content. Lowland rice also had a significant relationship between chlorophyll content 15 d after heading and protein content. Chlorophyll content plays an important part in protein accumulation in grain, especially in upland rice.

Parent-offspring correlation was measured in the chlorophyll content of 36 breeding lines in advanced generations between 1992 and 1993. A significant relationship was observed in chlorophyll content between generations ($r = 0.778^*$). It is therefore possible to select upland rice lines with low or high protein contents by measuring chlorophyll content about 2 wk before heading. ■

Parent-offspring correlation on chlorophyll content of upland rice lines. Ibaraki, Japan, 1992-93.

Correlation coefficients between protein content of brown rice and chlorophyll content in upland and lowland rice.^a Ibaraki, Japan.

Rice Variety	No.	Measuring data (day)						
		-45	-30	-15	Heading	+10	+15	+25
Upland	14	-0.018	0.297	0.891**	0.872**	0.792*	0.945**	0.942**
Lowland	14	-0.512	0.332	0.339	0.614	0.579	0.849*	0.812*

^a*, ** = significant at the 5% and 1% probability level, respectively.